

The effect of the halide anion on the optical properties of lead halide perovskites

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Abstract

Lead halide perovskites are promising semiconductors for solar energy conversion because of their electronic and optical properties. Using first principles we obtain these properties for the chlorine, bromine and iodine lead halide perovskites. In order to analyze the contributions of the different atoms and orbitals to the absorption coefficient, we split them into a many-species expansion. It allows the atomic and orbital contributions to be identified and quantified as a photon energy function.

Keywords: Perovskites; Optical properties; Photovoltaic; Semiconductors.

1. Introduction

Lead halide perovskites $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbX}_3$ ($\text{X}=\text{I}, \text{Br}, \text{Cl}$) with the methyl-ammonium organic cation $[\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3]^+$ are increasing in interest because of their optical and electrical properties (photoluminescence, electroluminescence, etc). In particular, perovskite solar cells are promising candidates for photovoltaics with efficiencies of 15-20 % [1,2]. The best solar cells have been obtained from $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ which has a bandgap of 1.55 eV, close to the optimum one for photovoltaic performance (~ 1.3 eV for a sunlight spectrum with the maximum concentration) [3–5]. Besides these compounds having low non-radiative recombination rates compared to other thin-film semiconductors. This is manifested in both the high external radiative efficiency and the

relatively small difference between the open-circuit voltage of the experimental cells and their energy bandgap transformed into voltage.

The increasing interest in perovskite does not only lie in the solar cell efficiencies but also in the novel device structures and new perovskite materials [6–8]. Organic/inorganic perovskites are compounds normally with an AMX_3 structure, where A is a large organic/inorganic cation, M a smaller metal cation and X an anion from the halide series. They form an MX_6 octahedral structure (Figure 1). In the $CH_3NH_3PbX_3$ organic lead halide perovskites analyzed in this work, the cation A is organic (Methylammonium $[CH_3NH_3]^+$), $M=Pb$, and $X=I, Br, Cl$. Both the optical absorption and the photoluminescence is related mainly to the Pb and X combination. The compounds with $X=I$ have smaller bandgaps and light emission at longer wavelengths while the bromides ($X=Br$) display higher bandgap and luminescence at shorter wavelengths [9–11]. Modification of the halide anion X^- changes the bond distance and/or angle of $X-Pb-X$. It is one of approaches for tuning the bandgap energy.

A detailed knowledge of the absorption coefficient is necessary for the optical design of single-gap and multi-junction solar cells. So far, only limited information on the $CH_3NH_3PbX_3$ optical properties is available [10,12–15]. In addition to the absorption coefficient, knowledge of the different contributions to the absorption coefficient can make it possible to identify the substitutions of organic/inorganic cations and anions that do not degrade the optical properties, and therefore the absorptive capacity of solar radiation.

To go deeply into both total and partial (split into the species contributions) absorption coefficients, the electronic and optical properties of several halide perovskites are evaluated using first principles. First we describe the methodology used in the calculations. After that, we describe the method for splitting the optical properties

into species contributions without simplifications in the methodology section. Then we describe, compare and discuss the results. Finally, we summarize the main conclusions.

2. Methodology

Calculations were made using density functional theory (DFT) [16,17] with periodic boundary conditions on the lead halide perovskites ($\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbX}_3$, X=I, Br, Cl). The generalized gradient approximation for the exchange-correlation functional was used as parameterized by Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof [18]. The outermost electrons are treated as valence electrons represented by a basis set made up of localized pseudoatomic orbitals [19]. The interactions of the valence electrons with the remaining ions is modeled by the Troullier–Martins [20] pseudopotentials expressed in the Kleinman–Bylander [21,22] form. The parameters of the structure used in the calculation were taken from reference [23]: $a = 6.460 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 6.442 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 6.526 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = 87.424^\circ$, $\beta = 86.798^\circ$, $\gamma = 92.852^\circ$ for X=I, $a = 6.050 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 6.035 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 6.103 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = 86.957^\circ$, $\beta = 85.914^\circ$, $\gamma = 92.957^\circ$ for X=Br, and $a = 5.761 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 5.747 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 5.824 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = 86.793^\circ$, $\beta = 85.328^\circ$, $\gamma = 93.215^\circ$ for X=Cl. The irreducible Brillouin zone for the electronic properties was sampled using 256 special k points.

The optical properties were obtained from the complex dielectric function ϵ_2 using the Kramers-Kronig relationships [24]. It is obtained as a photon energy function E using the band energies E_μ , the band occupations f_μ , and the momentum matrix elements $p_{\lambda\mu}$ between all of the bands:

$$\epsilon_2(E) \sim C \frac{1}{E^2} \sum_{\lambda} \sum_{\mu>\lambda} \int d\mathbf{k} (f_{\lambda} - f_{\mu}) |p_{\mu\lambda}|^2 \delta(E_{\mu} - E_{\lambda} - E) \quad (1)$$

405 special k points in the irreducible Brillouin zone were used for the optical properties. The momentum matrix elements $p_{\lambda\mu}$ can be split into inter-species

$p_{\mu\lambda} = \sum_A \sum_B p_{\mu\lambda}^{AB}$ (intra-species if A=B) or angular momentum inter-species contributions $p_{\mu\lambda}^{AB} = \sum_{l_A \in A} \sum_{l_B \in B} (p_{\mu\lambda}^{AB})_{l_A l_B}$ contributions. The $p_{\mu\lambda}^{AB}$ transition momentum matrix element couples the basis set functions on the A and B atoms of different species, and $(p_{\mu\lambda}^{AB})_{l_A l_B}$ the l_A shell-states located at the A atoms and the l_B shell-states located at the B atoms. The standard notation s, p, d , etc for $l=0, 1, 2$, etc is used.

With this breakdown the optical properties, depending on $|p_{\mu\lambda}|^2$, involve terms like $|(p_{\mu\lambda}^{AB})_{l_A l_B}| \cdot |(p_{\mu\lambda}^{CD})_{l_C l_D}|$. Then the optical properties can be split as a many-species expansion up to 4 species. In particular, for the absorption coefficient: $\alpha = \alpha(S) + A_{34}$. The first term $\alpha(S) = \sum_A \sum_B \alpha_{AB}$, with $\alpha_{AB} = \sum_{l_A \in A} \sum_{l_B \in B} \alpha_{l_A l_B}^{AB}$, includes intra-species (A=B) and inter-species (A≠B) terms. A_{34} includes the coupling of three or four different non-equivalent species terms. In general $\alpha(S) \gg A_{34}$, and the absorption coefficient can be approximated by $\alpha \approx \alpha(S)$. Nevertheless, the influence of this term will be evaluated in this work.

Note that the intra-species contributions, α_{AB} and $\alpha_{l_A l_B}^{AB}$ with A=B, contain all transitions between states of the atoms of the same species. They involve intra- and inter-atomic matrix elements. The intra-atomic elements correspond to transitions between states within an atom. Therefore they correspond to mono-centric matrix elements. The inter-atomic elements relate transitions between states of two atoms of the same species but at different position, i.e. they involve bi-centric matrix elements. When A≠B the transitions always involve transitions between atoms of different species and located at different positions. Therefore they are always inter-atomic with bi-centric matrix elements.

3. Results and discussion

From a structural point of view, the organic halide perovskites $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbX}_3$ ($\text{X}=\text{I}$, Br , Cl) consist of a framework of corner-sharing metal halide octahedra PbX_6 with the methylammonium cations $[\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3]^+$ fitting in the empty spaces between the octahedra (Figure 1). The bandgaps of these compounds have previously been studied both experimentally and theoretically. The range of experimental halide perovskites bandgaps reported in the literature are: 1.55-1.61 eV (1.55 [25], 1.61 [26]) for $\text{X}=\text{I}$, 2.00-2.44 eV (2.00 [25], 2.3 [27], 2.44 eV [15]) for $\text{X}=\text{Br}$, and 2.88-3.13 eV (2.88-3.13[10], 3.11 eV [25]) for $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$. The bandgaps obtained theoretically using DFT with several exchange-correlation functionals and basis sets are in the range 1.23-1.85 eV (1.23-1.85 eV [28], 1.53 [29], 1.57 [30]) for iodine, 1.80 [30]-1.89 [29] eV for bromide, and 2.34 [30]-2.36 [29] for chloride perovskites. These calculated bandgaps are in general good agreement with reported experimental values. The bandgaps obtained with more sophisticated and more computationally expensive methods, such as GW are 1.31-1.73 [31–33] for $\text{X}=\text{I}$, 2.34– 2.83 [32,34] for $\text{X}=\text{Br}$, and 3.07– 3.59 [32,34] for $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$. The bandgaps obtained in this work are 1.60, 2.12, and 2.50 eV for $\text{X}=\text{I}$, Br , and Cl respectively. These values are within those obtained experimentally except in case of $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$ where it is slightly underestimated. Nonetheless, this value is closer to the experimental values than many of the values reported theoretically in the literature.

An analysis of the projected density of states (PDOS) reveals that the valence band (VB) top is made up predominantly of the $p(\text{X})$ orbitals, and the bottom of the conduction band (CB) is mainly of a $p(\text{Pb})$ character with a smaller contribution from the $p(\text{X})$ orbitals (Figure 2). It is in agreement with other references in the literature [29,30,35]. Therefore for $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbX}_3$ mixed-halide compounds the $p(\text{X})$ states have little influence on the CB edge but leads to substantial changes in the VB edge,

therefore influencing the energy bandgap. Since the energies of the $p(X)$ states are $p(\text{Cl}) < p(\text{Br}) < p(\text{I})$ (Figure 2), the bandgaps in ascending order are for $X=\text{I}$, Br and Cl halide perovskites. The increase in the bandgap energy can be consistent with the ionic character of the Pb-X bond in the PbX_6 octahedra.

Halide perovskites are one of the most promising compounds for the next generation of solar cells. A great deal of experimental effort has been made on the optical properties [10,12–15,36]. The sunlight absorption is determined mainly by the absorption coefficient. But the absorption coefficient, measured experimentally or calculated theoretically, does not give us any information on the main contributions of the species or the orbitals. For this reason we have developed a method for splitting the optical properties into different contributions (methodology section). This allows us to analyze the main contributions and to relate the optical properties with the composition and the structure of the materials. The optical absorption coefficients split into intra-species transition and angular momentum species contributions are shown in Figures 3 and 4 respectively. Our result reproduces the spectral features of the experimental room temperature absorbance spectrum from reference [12] for $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbX}_3$ ($X=\text{I}$, Br , Cl). In Figures 3 and 4 the shaded areas correspond to these experimental absorption bands. For the iodine ($X=\text{I}$) perovskite (Figure 3a) the optical absorption band between 2.5-2.7 eV is due to the Pb-Pb intra-specie transition. When these transitions are split further into the most important angular momentum species contributions (Figure 4a) the results indicate that these transitions mainly came from of the $s(\text{Pb})\text{-p}(\text{Pb})$, and with a lower proportion of $s(\text{I})\text{-p}(\text{I})$ and $p(\text{Pb})\text{-p}(\text{I})$. In agreement with our results this band had been attributed [13] to the transition from $\text{Pb}^{2+}(6s)$ to $\text{Pb}^{2+}(6p)$. Our results also reproduce the experimental large absorption band between 3.2-3.5 eV [12], and the decrease between 3.5 and 4 eV. The pronounced absorption band between 3.2-3.5 eV is brought

about, in descending order of importance, by the I-I, Pb-I and Pb-Pb species transition (Figure 3a), i.e. mainly by s(I)-p(I), p(Pb)-p(I) and s(Pb)-p(Pb) (Figure 4a). Our results are also in accordance with those of reference [14] in which three peaks appear in the absorption spectra at about 1.65, 2.20, and 3.10 eV. The first peak at about 1.65 eV is mainly due to the s(Pb)-p(Pb) excitation. The second, which peaks around 2.20 eV, is also mainly because of the s(Pb)-p(Pb) transitions, with a lower contribution of the s(I)-p(I) excitation. Finally, the peak at around 3.10 eV is due to similar contributions from s(Pb)-p(Pb), s(I)-p(I), and p(Pb)-p(I).

In contrast to the iodine perovskite, the X=Cl and Br compounds show sharper absorption peaks (Figure 3b, 3c, 4b, and 4c). The peaks in the spectra of chlorides are sharper than those of bromides and the bromides are sharper than those of iodides. As before, our results agree well with the optical absorption and photoluminescence experimental results [10,12,15]. The main contributions to the absorption coefficient can be deduced from these figures. The band absorption peaks with X=Cl shifted towards high energy with respect to the X=Br peaks are in agreement with the experimental absorbance spectrum [12]. Therefore, the bandgap and the absorption coefficient can be shifted monotonously towards high energy with an increase in the Cl. This is because the electronegativity of the Cl is larger than that of the Br and I. The bandgaps (energy difference between the CB and VB edges) are mainly determined by the p(X) (p(Pb)) states which made up mostly the top of the VB (bottom of the CB). As the p(Cl) states have lower energy (due to larger Cl electronegativity) than the other p(Br) and p(I) states, the VB top for X=Cl has lower energy (Figure 2), i.e. larger bandgap. The absorption coefficient is different from zero for energies larger than the energy bandgap. Therefore also the absorption coefficient moves towards higher energy with the increase of chlorine in the perovskite composition. Additionally, the lower

energy of the anion states (because of the higher electronegativity) the resulting energy bands are narrower (Figure 2) resulting in sharper absorption peaks.

In all lead halide perovskites with the methylammonium cation, for energy close to the bandgap, the most important contributions are the Pb-Pb intra-species transitions, and with a lower proportion the X-X. Therefore the optical properties are determined mainly by the PbX_6 octahedra. The methylammonium cations do not directly contribute the VB and CB band edges. Neither do they contribute with terms of one and two species (intra- and inter-specie terms respectively) to the optical properties. However, this organic cation indirectly affects the Pb-X bonds, and therefore, the geometry and the electronic and optical properties [12].

In order to evaluate the contribution of the organic cation to the optical properties in greater depth, the contributions of three and 4 species terms (A_{34}) are also shown in Figure 3. The 3 and 4 species terms are only present when the number of species in the compound is greater than 3 and 4 respectively. Its contribution tends to be greater when the species number is larger. For the perovskites analyzed in this work, with five species (C, H, N, Pb, and X), the number of one (intra-specie), two (inter-specie), three, and four different species terms in the split of the absorption coefficients are 5, 10, 10, and 5 respectively. Therefore the number of 3 and 4 species terms is similar to the number of intra and inter-species terms. This does not happen in the most common binary semiconductors (II-VI, II-VI, etc) where the 3 and 4 species terms are absent. Note that this decomposition is exact and serves to evaluate the different contributions to the absorption coefficient. Sometimes the interpretation of the contributions to the optical properties is done qualitatively using the PDOS. But the PDOS does not take into account the transition probabilities. For this reason the simplified analysis based on the PDOS is sometimes inadequate [37]. Of course PDOS

is appropriate for understanding electronic structures, but inappropriate for analyzing photo-excitation properties.

From the Figure 3, the three and four species contributions are lower than the Pb-Pb intra-specie contribution, except for the X=I and energies between 2.3-3.8 eV. Therefore, this term is as important as the aforementioned ones (I-I, Pb-I and Pb-Pb) for the experimental large absorption band between 3.2-3.5 eV [12]. It indicates that the organic cation contributes indirectly to the optical properties via three and 4 species terms.

The content of lead in these compounds can generate environmental and toxicity problems. This aspect is increasingly important in the legislations of many countries. Therefore, although technically these lead compounds are promising for solar cells, their future development may be negatively affected by these problems. Therefore it would be suitable to replace the Pb with other cations to avoid them. This replacement of the Pb by another element M should maintain the high values of the absorption coefficient without deteriorating the perovskite absorption capacity.

4. Conclusions

The electronic and optical properties of lead halide perovskites are obtained using first principles based on the DFT. The edges of the VB and CB are predominantly made up of p(X) and p(Pb) states respectively. Because of the importance of the absorption coefficient on the solar radiation absorption capacity we have obtained the differences between the halide anions, compared them with experimental results, and analyzed them.

In order to relate the atomic composition and the structure with the optical properties we have broken down the optical properties into a many-species expansion.

This allows us to identify and quantify the different contributions to the optical properties as a function of the photon energy without approximations. Near the gap the most important contribution is brought about by Pb-Pb (s(Pb)-p(Pb)) intra-species transitions. The characteristic absorption band above 3 eV is brought about mainly by s(Pb)-p(Pb), and with a lower contribution by p(Pb)-p(X) and s(X)-p(X) transitions. These latter contributions decrease from iodine to chlorine, i.e. when increasing the electronegativity of the halide. Therefore, in order to avoid the toxicity problems generated by lead and maintain high absorption, it would be necessary to replace the Pb with another element M that also had a high M-M intra-specie contribution to the absorption coefficient.

In the case of iodine, the organic cation, via terms of 3 and 4 species, also contribute indirectly to the experimental absorption band between 3.2-3.5 eV.

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Figure 1: Crystalline structure of the Perovskite $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbX}_3$ semiconductors. The shaded areas indicate the PbX_6 octahedra.

Figure 2: $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbX}_3$ ($X=\text{Cl}$, Br , and I) PDOS on species states with a greater contribution to the VB and CB edges. The CB edge has been chosen as the origin of the energy. Pb_x indicates the Pb-PDOS in the halide perovskite $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbX}_3$.

Figure 3: $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbX}_3$ absorption coefficient split into the most important species contributions (left y axis) with (a) $\text{X}=\text{I}$, (b) $\text{X}=\text{Br}$, and (c) $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$. The total absorption coefficient is represented in the right-hand y axis. The shaded areas correspond to the absorption peaks of the room temperature absorbance experimental spectrum from reference [12]. A_{34} represents the contribution of 3 and 4 species terms to the absorption coefficient.

Figure 4: Most important angular momentum species contributions to the $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbX}_3$ absorption coefficient with (a) $X=\text{I}$, (b) $X=\text{Br}$, and (c) $X=\text{Cl}$. The shaded areas correspond to the absorption peaks of the room temperature absorbance experimental spectrum from reference [12].